

Reflectance

Editors: Casey Jenson, R. Chelsea Nagy, & Alison K. Post

Clouds Form Over North Africa
(Credit: [NASA Image of the Day](#))

Quick Updates

- A paper was published by former Earth Lab graduate student [Remote Sensing-Based Forest Modeling Reveals Positive Effects of Functional Diversity on Productivity at Local Spatial Scale](#)
- Earth Lab's Interim Analytics Hub Director & Data Scientist Cibele Amaral published [Drivers of mangrove vulnerability and resilience to tropical cyclones in the North Atlantic Basin](#)
- The NC RISCC published their [2023 Practitioner Survey Report](#)
- ESILL Director, Jennifer Balch released two Op-Eds in The Washington Post; [Our wildfire problem is growing beyond our ability to tame it](#), and [Wildfires were once slowed by night and winter. Not anymore](#)
- Laura Lipuma, CIRES Scientific Communications Editor, hosted a workshop on [Writing Engaging Science blogs](#) during our EDS Seminar
- About a dozen Earth Lab team members attended and spoke at the annual [Ecological Society of America conference](#) in August

Graduate Research Assistants

This summer Earth Lab had 10 Graduate Research Assistants working on various collaborative projects. At the end of the summer they each gave an ignite talk & wrote blogs summarizing their work. A few of these GRA projects are featured below. Read each student's full project summary in our [blog](#). (Tip: search for these on our blog by using the tag 'Graduate Student Research')

Meghan Hayden

Biodiversity across scales:
Mapping functional diversity with remote sensing to assess scale dependencies in biodiversity monitoring

Brendan Hobart

How grass invasion and fire affect songbirds of the sage

Behzad Vahedi

Towards Near-Real-Time fire event perimeter mapping using optical and radar data fusion

Anna LoPresti

How do prescribed burns provide value to people? Evaluating the ecosystem service benefits of intentional fire

Janushi Shastri

Macrosystems project:
cross calibration
Python tool

Jerry Gammie
Multiscale
machine learning
for prescribed
burns

Max Cook

Mapping rooftops using satellite imagery and Zillow data

2023 Summer Field Season

This summer an Earth Lab field team continued work on two projects related to the recovery of forested ecosystems following wildfire and other disturbances.

1) the team flew a drone with a high-resolution camera over burned area transects to collect images from many different locations. The images will be processed to create 3-dimensional models of forest recovery.

2) the team flew a drone with a multispectral sensor over plots with variable vegetation cover. Later, the team returned with the resulting mosaiced images in-hand to map vegetation cover digitally directly onto the imagery. Spectral signatures from the mapped vegetation will be used to unmix the Landsat satellite archive and provide information on recovery trajectories of plant functional types following different combinations of disturbances.

The field team at the Overland Fire burn scar near Jamestown, CO. From left to right: Steelle Stevens, Nathan Korinek, Nayani Ilngakoon, Katie Ellis, Ian MacKeigan, Tyler McIntosh

Undergraduate researchers Steelle Stevens & Katie Ellis prepare a vegetation survey plot by collecting the GPS location of a ground control point (GCP).

Earth Data Analytics Students

See student projects from our 2023 [Earth Data Analytics Professional Graduate Certificate](#) program below & read their full projects in our [blog](#).

Forest Recovery: Post-Wildfire Vegetation Analysis after Chimney Tops 2 Fire

By Stepan Bryleev

Using Google Earth Engine and NEON spatial data, Stepan calculated several pre- & post-fire vegetation indices to identify regrowth dynamics inside the perimeter of the Chimney Tops 2 fire.

Landslide Detection using Synthetic Aperture Radar and Multispectral Imagery

By Nasim Mozafar Amiri

Nasim examined two specific landslide incidents using time series of SAR images and calculated the Normalized Difference Watershed Index (NDWI) using multispectral imagery.

Evaluating Vegetation Health & Land Management in Brighton, CO

By Matison Lakstigala

Matison gathered and assessed data to calculate the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) for five study areas to gauge drought indicators in the city of Brighton, CO.

Spilled Secrets: Uncovering the Effects of Oil Spills on Wildlife in the North Sea

By Ryan Boarman

Ryan used oil slick data and species distribution maps to investigate the effects of oil spills on the North Sea's wildlife.

Discarded Seafloor-Objects: A Hidden World Beneath the Waves

By Allison Buchanan and Robyn Marowitz
Allison and Robyn used multiple data types in a machine learning model to analyze the state of the ocean floor in their study location & infer the fate of discarded objects on the seafloor.

Taking the Low Road: Floodplain Connectivity in Boulder, CO

By Lindsay Chipman and Julia Sobczak

Using data from aerial imagery drones, elevation models (LiDAR), histograms, and simulations, Lindsay & Julia visualized floodplain connectivity to help land-use planners design and implement restoration strategies in the St. Vrain watershed.

Summer Team Socials

Over the summer, Earth Lab held team social events including a baked-goods potluck, a yard games picnic, and a trivia pizza party to celebrate our cohort of GRAs.

Check out our Instagram highlight to see more [@earthlabcu](#).

ESIL Innovation Summit

In May, Earth Lab helped host ESIL's first annual summit. The [2023 Innovation Summit](#) took place over three days in late May to build the network & advance Environmental Data Science (EDS) & inclusion. Participants heard from keynote speakers & worked in breakout groups on innovative science projects of their choosing. Check out [ESIL's website](#) for upcoming events including working groups and hackathons.

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